

Supplementary Figure 1. Identification and quantification of PICs and satellite cells in murine hind-limb muscle. (A-C) Immunohistochemistry of paraffin embedded hind-limb muscle from 10 day old mice identifies PW1^{pos} cells. PICs are located within interstitial spaces (B) and satellite cells located under the basal lamina (C). (D-E) Quantification of PW1^{pos} PICs and satellite cells in the hind-limb muscle of mice at 3d, 10d, 21d and 2 years of age, expressed as a percentage of total nuclei (D) and per 100 muscle fibres (E). (F) Ratio of PICs to satellite cells in neonatal to aged mice. Data are Mean ± SD, n=3 per group.